

ENDOTHELIAL FUNCTION ASSESSMENT IN PREECLAMPTIC PREGNANCIES WITH INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL CONDITIONS

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Relevance of the Study. According to modern perspectives, preeclampsia (PE) is a pregnancy-induced hypertensive condition characterized by damage to organs such as the kidneys, liver, and the hemostatic system, as well as neurological symptoms and fetal distress [2,4]. Many authors note that moderate to severe forms of PE are increasingly prevalent. These forms can lead to fetal complications and multi-organ failure in the mother. This underscores the need to predict and prevent the development of complications in other organs and tissues, including periodontal tissues, in cases of PE [1,3].

Aim of the Study. To assess the status of endothelial dysfunction in pregnant women with inflammatory periodontal diseases who are diagnosed with preeclampsia.

Materials and Methods. A total of 120 pregnant women aged 18 to 49 years were examined using clinical, functional, and laboratory methods. The participants were divided into three groups:

- **Main group:** 60 pregnant women with diagnosed preeclampsia.
- **Comparison group:** 40 pregnant women with no signs of preeclampsia (physiological pregnancy).
- **Control group:** 20 non-pregnant women of reproductive age.

Results. In the main group, the incidence of moderate and severe periodontitis was found to be 2.3 and 5.66 times higher, respectively, compared to the group with physiological pregnancies. This suggests that vascular wall changes are occurring, reflected by a reduction in the anticoagulant and fibrinolytic activity of the endothelium. Altered thromboresistance in the endothelial lining is considered a key factor contributing to the progression of periodontal inflammation.

In patients from the main group, decreased anticoagulant activity was linked to reduced secretion of antithrombin III by the endothelium. Significant differences were observed between groups in terms of antithrombin III levels before and after cuff testing. In the control group, the values were $97.61 \pm 5.9\%$ and $124.32 \pm 8.62\%$, respectively. In the comparison group, the levels dropped to $91.43 \pm 5.31\%$ and $112.32 \pm 6.4\%$, indicating normal physiological changes during pregnancy. However, in the main group, these values were significantly lower at $74.51 \pm 4.06\%$ and $88.12 \pm 4.54\%$ ($p < 0.05$).

Based on these indicators, an index for endothelial anticoagulant activity was calculated to assess vascular condition, which resulted in 1.28 ± 0.08 for the control group, 1.23 ± 0.06 for the comparison group, and 1.18 ± 0.09 for the main group. This statistically significant decrease in the main group highlights impaired endothelial function.

Conclusion. The findings indicate that pregnant women with PE demonstrate reduced hypocoagulant activity, implying the presence of pathological conditions such as hypercoagulation and endothelial dysfunction. Furthermore, increased Hageman factor-dependent fibrinolysis time and reduced endothelial fibrinolytic activity suggest a higher risk of vascular thrombosis. These systemic changes may be sufficient to cause localized chronic inflammation in the periodontal tissues. Elevated levels of homocysteine and endothelin-1 are potential indicators of serous inflammation and clinical symptoms in the periodontal tissues of these patients.

References:

1. Sibai B.M., Stella C.L. (2009). Diagnosis and management of atypical preeclampsia-eclampsia. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 200(5): 481.e1–481.e7.
2. Van Winkelen P., Van der Velden U. (2002). The role of inflammation in the pathogenesis of preeclampsia and periodontal disease: a common link? *Journal of Clinical Periodontology*, 29(9): 768–777.
3. Konopka T., Paradowska-Stolarz A. (2012). Periodontal diseases and systemic diseases: Pre-eclampsia and other pregnancy complications. *Archives of Medical Science*, 8(4): 691–697.
4. Redman C.W.G., Sargent I.L. (2005). Latest advances in understanding preeclampsia. *Science*, 308(5728): 1592–1594.

